

LINGUISTIC-COMMUNICATIVE TEACHING OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TO ARCHITECTURE STUDENTS

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Annotation. This article is about the study of professional orientation of FL teaching in the linguo-didactic aspect is designed to strengthen the general knowledge of FL (grammar, vocabulary, phonetics, syntax) acquired before entering the university, supplementing them with lexical and grammatical knowledge.

Key words: communicative competence, foreign language, linguo-didactic, communicative culture.

As a result of today's international development of engineering technologies and the increasing complexity of public relations related to it, there is an increase in the need for highly qualified engineering personnel who are ready and able to communicate in a foreign language in the professional field and constantly improve their professional skills.

Variable teaching of a foreign language in the architectural direction of higher educational institutions and teaching in a foreign language is the formation of the foreign language component of the communicative competence of the future engineer. At the same time, this type of training has great potential as a means of developing a professional person who possesses a set of qualities that are required in the modern, complex labor market and make high demands on the employee. The ability to use FL (foreign language) in this direction depends on a number of aspects.

The study of professional orientation of FL teaching in the linguo-didactic aspect is designed to strengthen the general knowledge of FL (grammar, vocabulary, phonetics, syntax) acquired before entering the university, supplementing them with lexical and grammatical knowledge. The characteristic of the chosen specialty is to teach the formation and formation of opinions about FL.

Lingvo-communicative is a direction related to the creation of texts and oral statements, teaching to perform communicative actions in conditions determined by professional necessity. At the moment, almost all subjects aimed at teaching

communication in professional communication settings are not included in the curricula of bachelor's and master's programs. When this is combined with the low level of general culture of the listeners, it leads to difficulties in written and spoken communication even in their native languages.

Obviously, if a person cannot consistently describe his activities and present his results in his native language, he cannot do it in a foreign language. This gives rise to the idea of using the search for meaning in the foreign language to improve meaningful speech in the native language and then return to the new level of foreign language speech.

According to T.S. Serova, "Communicative culture cannot be taught through a lecture course, several trainings, optional courses, and implementation of practice. Only communication, such as exchange, information, and the production of ideas, develops a person, and therefore becomes the reason and basis for the formation of knowledge"¹.

The next aspect is cognitive. On the one hand, the development of foreign language knowledge of professional importance is important in terms of improving professional competences. At the same time, when teaching FL in the context of specialization or teaching specialization through FL, it is important to have new concepts, propositions, interrelationships of symbols (sometimes deeper than teaching from 0 - because it is more difficult). And the characters with the cognitive structure of the person and their inclusion in this composition.

An important feature of a foreign language as an academic subject is that it can be supplemented with the subject content of any engineering or humanitarian discipline. Thus, a foreign language can be considered as a basis for creating integrated educational courses.

One of the promising directions of interrelated development of cognitive and communicative competences of a future specialist is the study of a foreign language not only as a subject of study, but mainly as a teaching tool and learning disciplines.

¹ Серова, Т. С. Формирование иноязычных коммуникативно-речевых компетенций как условия мобильности студентов в процессе интеграции в европейскую образовательную систему [Текст] / Т. С. Серова // Технические университеты: интеграция с европейской и мировой системами образования: материалы IV Междунар. Конф. (Россия, Ижевск, 21-23 апреля 2010 г.). В 3 т. Т.1. – Ижевск, Изд-во ИжГТУ, 2010. – С. 506-516.

The main goal of bilingual education is to achieve a high level of professional, foreign language and intercultural competence by students. Bilingualism is an interdisciplinary phenomenon, and its problems are studied by such disciplines as linguistics, translation studies, psycholinguistics, psychology, sociology, and pedagogy. When studying the linguistic aspect of bilingualism, we must take into account linguistic competence, that is, the level of knowledge of each of the two languages, and the functional distribution of languages in one or another field.

Bilingual education poses very serious problems for teachers and especially students, so it is important to study the psychological aspects related to it, especially the psychological barriers between students. In this, we rely on the work of O. Khudobina in which, based on the generalization of the researches of linguists and psychologists, the typology of language barriers due to the specific characteristics of the "foreign language" academician is determined by the science itself and the specific conditions of bilingual education. Adopting a typology that includes organizational, semantic, listening and speaking, reading and writing, creative activity, knowledge, emotional and other psychological obstacles, creating special didactic, organizational, psychological and material conditions necessary to successfully overcome them in the conditions of the bilingual education process we understand the need. At the same time, we believe that overcoming psychological barriers can significantly influence the communicative and cognitive aspects of integrated bilingual education to motivate students and develop their communicative interest in the professional field.

In our opinion, within the framework of the student's educational activity, modeling of his professional activity in a foreign language as a future specialist and the most complete consideration of the principles of contextual learning proposed by A.A. Verbitsky (ensure the student's personal involvement in educational activities; the content, forms and conditions of professional activity in educational activities modeling; the principle of problematic content; the principle of the leading role of joint activity, etc.), probably, a number of problems are encountered in the process of teaching in a specially developed integrated language. Training based on the active use of relevant, authentic Russian and foreign language professional information allows students to transition from education to semi-professional and professional activities in the language systems of their native and foreign languages.

In conclusion, it should be said that at the initial stage of development, bilingual education was naturally connected with humanities (history, cultural studies, sociology, law, etc.). Later, there were jobs related to teaching mathematics, informatics and computers. Until recently, the issue of bilingual education in engineering disciplines itself (eg, mechanical engineering, thermal architecture, construction) has not been affected at all.

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